

Application of Marks to Count the Number of Isomers Derived from Trigonal Bipyramidal Molecules

Jane Rimberia

Mathematics and Actuarial Science Department, Kenyatta University, P. O. Box 43844-00100, Nairobi, Kenya

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 27 May 2026</p> <p>Corresponding Author: Jane Rimberia</p>	<p>The concept of mark of a permutation group was introduced by Burnside in 1911. Redfield rediscovered marks in 1930s but his work was not published until 1984. He used marks to count group reduced distributions according to their symmetry groups. Marks have been used by several other authors; Sheehan [10] used marks to count the number of graphs with a given automorphism group, Lloyd [7] counted isomers using marks, Kamuti [4] used marks to find subdegrees of primitive permutation representations of $PGL(2, q)$, Kimani et. al. [5] used marks to compute the ranks and subdegrees of the symmetric group acting on ordered pairs and ordered triples while Rimberia and Kamuti [9] used marks to find the subdegrees of primitive permutation representations of the symmetric group S_5. In this paper, we enumerate the number of stereoisomers derived from trigonal bipyramidal molecules using the mark version of Redfield superposition theorem. Results show that Iodotricarbonyl (triphenylphosphine) – cobalt (1) complex has 4 stereoisomers while a trigonal bipyramidal complex of the type $MABCDE$ has 20 stereoisomers.</p>
<p>KEYWORDS: Marks, table of marks, isomers</p>	

1. INTRODUCTION

The concept of mark of a permutation group has been defined by three different authors (See Burnside [1], White [11] and Ivanov et al. [2]). However, these three definitions were shown to be equivalent in Kamuti [3]. In this paper we shall use the third definition. Marks can be used in various other fields apart from Mathematics. For example in Chemistry, they are used in enumeration of isomers. These are chemically distinguishable compounds which share the same chemical formula. Now, suppose $G_j \leq G_i \leq G$ and $(G_{j_1}, G_{j_2}, \dots, G_{j_n})$ is a complete set of conjugacy class representatives of subgroups of G_i that are conjugate to G_j in G , then the mark of G_j in the coset representation $G/(G_i)$ is the number of cosets of G_i in G left fixed by every permutation of G_j and is given by

$$m(G_j, G_i, G) = \sum_{k=1}^n |N_G(G_{j_k}) : N_{G_i}(G_{j_k})| \quad (\text{Ivanov et. al. [2]}).$$

In particular when $n = 1$, G_j is conjugate in G_i to all subgroups $G_{j'}$ that are contained in G_i and conjugate to G_j in G and

$$m(G_j, G_i, G) = |N_G(G_j) : N_{G_i}(G_j)|.$$

Next, if $\{H_1, H_2, \dots, H_t\}$ is a set of representatives of all distinct conjugacy classes of subgroups of H in G , ordered such that $|H_1| \leq |H_2| \leq \dots \leq |H_t| = |H|$. Form a matrix $M = (m_{ij})$, where $m_{ij} = m(H_j, H_i, H)$. We call M the table of marks of H (Ivanov et al. [2]).

2. PRELIMINARIES

Definition 2.1 (Stereoisomers)

Stereoisomers are chemical compounds distinguishable by virtue of the fact that the three-dimensional arrangement of their constituents differ.

Definition 2.2 (Molecule)

A molecule in this paper will be regarded as consisting of a skeleton on which there are various sites, with one ligand occupying each site.

Theorem 2.1: (Redfield – Read Superposition Theorem)
(See Lloyd (B) [6]).

The number of group reduced distributions arising from double action of S_n and $G_1 \times G_2 \times \dots \times G_q$ on $q \times n$ arrays is equal to

$$N\left(\text{Grf}(G_1) * \text{Grf}(G_2) * \dots * \text{Grf}(G_q)\right),$$

where $N(P)$ denotes the sum of the coefficients in the polynomial P and the binary operation $*$ is defined as

RULE 1: For identical monomials

$$s_1^{j_1} s_2^{j_2} \dots * s_1^{k_1} s_2^{k_2} \dots = 1^{j_1} j_1! 2^{j_2} j_2! \dots s_1^{j_1} s_2^{j_2} \dots$$

RULE 2: If $(j_1, j_2, \dots) \neq (k_1, k_2, \dots)$, then

$$s_1^{j_1} s_2^{j_2} \dots * s_1^{k_1} s_2^{k_2} \dots = 0$$

RULE 3: The composition extends to general polynomials by linearity.

3. ENUMERATION OF ISOMERS USING THE MARK VERSION OF REDFIELD SUPERPOSITION THEOREM

In Theorem 2.1, the number of distinct arrays (group reduced distributions) is equal to the number of orbits of the arrays under the combined action of the site group A , ligand group B and S_n . Each group reduced distribution has its own symmetry group. For isomers, this is the group of symmetry operations that permute identical ligands occupying equivalent sites on the skeleton of the molecule. The number with specified symmetry group can be counted using marks of a permutation group.

Redfield [8] considered a more general problem in which he replaced the symmetric group S_n acting on intact columns of the array by a general group F called the frame group. In his terminology, A and B are called range groups and must be subgroups of F . The F -mark vectors corresponding to the action of F on the left cosets of A and B in F are denoted by $\underline{m}(A)$ and $\underline{m}(B)$ respectively.

Theorem 3.1: (The Mark Version of Redfield Superposition Theorem) (Lloyd [7]).

Let $M(F)$ be the table of marks of a frame group F , the rows and columns of which correspond to representative subgroups H_1, H_2, \dots, H_t and let $A, B \leq F$ be range groups. The number ζ_i of group reduced distributions which have symmetry group conjugate to H_i may be obtained by the following algorithm:

- i). Calculate the F – mark vectors $\underline{m}(A)$ and $\underline{m}(B)$ of A and B respectively.
- ii). Multiply them together coordinate by coordinate to obtain the vector $\underline{m}(A) \square \underline{m}(B)$.
- iii). Find the vector $\zeta = (\zeta_1, \zeta_2, \dots, \zeta_t)$ such that $\underline{m}(A) \square \underline{m}(B) = \zeta M(F)$.

3.1.1 Examples in enumeration of isomers of trigonal bipyramidal molecules

a) Stereoisomers of Iodotricarbonyl(triphenylphosphine) – cobalt (1) complex,

This is a trigonal bipyramidal complex of the type MX_3YU and so the frame group F is S_5 . Now, S_5 has 19 conjugacy classes of subgroups. These are;

- H_1 - Identity.
- H_2 - 10 conjugate subgroups of order 2 generated by permutations of the form (ab) .
- H_3 - 15 conjugate subgroups of order 2 generated by permutations of the form $(ab)(cd)$.
- H_4 - 10 conjugate cyclic subgroups of order 3.
- H_5 - 15 conjugate cyclic subgroups of order 4.
- H_6 - 5 conjugate subgroups of order 4 isomorphic to $C_2 \times C_2$ generated by permutations of the form $(ab)(cd)$.
- H_7 - 15 conjugate subgroups of order 4 isomorphic to $C_2 \times C_2$ generated by permutations of the form (ab) and $(ab)(cd)$.
- H_8 - 6 conjugate cyclic subgroups of order 5.
- H_9 - 10 conjugate subgroups of order 6 isomorphic D_3 generated by permutations of the form (ab) and (abc) .
- H_{10} - 10 conjugate cyclic subgroups of order 6.
- H_{11} - 10 conjugate subgroups of order 6 isomorphic to D_3 generated by permutations of the form $(ab)(cd)$ and (abc) .
- H_{12} - 15 conjugate subgroups of order 8 isomorphic to D_4 .
- H_{13} - 6 conjugate subgroups of order 10 isomorphic to D_5 .
- H_{14} - 5 conjugate subgroups of order 12 isomorphic to A_4 .
- H_{15} - 10 conjugate subgroups of order 12 isomorphic to $S_3 \times C_2$.
- H_{16} - 6 conjugate subgroups of order 20 isomorphic to $\langle (abcd), (aedcb) \rangle$.
- H_{17} - 5 conjugate subgroups of order 24 isomorphic to S_4 .
- H_{18} - A_5 .
- H_{19} - S_5 .

The corresponding table of marks of S_5 is as shown in Table 3.1

Table 3.1: Table of marks of S_5

	H	H ₂	H ₃	H ₄	H ₅	H ₆	H ₇	H ₈	H ₉	H ₁	H ₁₉								
	1									0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	
$G(/H_1)$	1																		
	2																		
$G(/H_2)$	6	6																	
	0																		
$G(/H_3)$	6	0	4																
	0																		
$G(/H_4)$	4	0	0	4															
	0																		
$G(/H_5)$	3	0	2	0	2														
	0																		
$G(/H_6)$	3	0	6	0	0	6													
	0																		
$G(/H_7)$	3	6	2	0	0	0	2												
	0																		
$G(/H_8)$	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	4											
	4																		
$G(/H_9)$	2	6	0	2	0	0	0	0	2										
	0																		
$G(/H_{10})$	2	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	2									
	0																		
$G(/H_{11})$	2	0	4	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	2								
	0																		
$G(/H_{12})$	1	3	3	0	1	3	1	0	0	0	0	1							
	5																		
$G(/H_{13})$	1	0	4	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	2						
	2																		
$G(/H_{14})$	1	0	2	4	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2					
	0																		
$G(/H_{15})$	1	4	2	1	0	0	2	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1				
	0																		
$G(/H_{16})$	6	0	2	0	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1			
$G(/H_{17})$	5	3	1	2	1	1	1	0	2	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1		
$G(/H_{18})$	2	0	2	2	0	2	0	2	0	0	2	0	2	2	0	0	0	2	
$G(/H_{19})$	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

The site group A is a non – cyclic group of order 6. On the other hand, the frame group S_5 has two different types of non – cyclic subgroups of order 6, that is H_9 and H_{11} .

Since the cycle index of H_{11} acting on the set $X = \{a, b, c, d, e\}$ is equal to that of the site group A

acting on the same set, then A must be isomorphic to H_{11} .

The ligand group $B = S_1 \times S_3 \times S_1$, which is a non-cyclic group of order 6. B is isomorphic to subgroup H_9 of S_5 since its cycle index is equal to that of H_9 acting on the set $X = \{a, b, c, d, e\}$.

From rows 11 and 9 of Table 3.1,

$$\underline{m}(A) = (20, 0, 4, 2, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 2, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0)$$

and

$$\underline{m}(B) = (20, 6, 0, 2, 0, 0, 0, 0, 2, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0)$$

So

Figure 1: Stereoisomers with symmetry group conjugate to H_1

Figure 2: Stereoisomer with symmetry group conjugate to H_4

b) Stereoisomers of hydridocarbonyl ethylene(bis-triphenylphosphine) – rhodium (I) complex,

This is a trigonal bipyramidal complex of the type $MXYU_2V$, hence the frame group $F = S_5$. The ligand group $B = S_1 \times S_1 \times S_2 \times S_1$, which is a group of order 2 and S_5 has two different types of subgroups of order 2, H_2 and H_3 . Since the cycle index of H_2 acting on the set $X = \{a, b, c, d, e\}$ is equal to that of B , then B must be isomorphic to H_2 . From rows 11 and 2 of Table 3.1,

$$\underline{m}(A) = (20, 0, 4, 2, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 2, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0)$$

and

$$\underline{m}(A) \square \underline{m}(B) = (400, 0, 0, 4, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0)$$

Expressed as a linear combination of rows of Table 3.1,

$$\underline{m}(A) \square \underline{m}(B) = 3(120, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0) + (40, 0, 0, 4, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0),$$

so

$$\underline{m}(A) \square \underline{m}(B) = 3\underline{m}(H_1) + \underline{m}(H_4).$$

Hence by Theorem 3.1, the complex has 4 stereoisomers, three with symmetry group conjugate to H_1 and one with symmetry group conjugate to H_4 . Their corresponding drawings are;

$$\underline{m}(B) = (60, 6, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0)$$

So

$$\underline{m}(A) \square \underline{m}(B) = (1200, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0)$$

Expressed as a linear combination of rows of Table 3.1,

$$\underline{m}(A) \square \underline{m}(B) = 10(120, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0)$$

,
so

$$\underline{m}(A) \square \underline{m}(B) = 10\underline{m}(H_1).$$

Therefore, by Theorem 3.1 the complex has 10 stereoisomers with symmetry group conjugate to H_1 .

c) Stereoisomers of a trigonal bipyramidal complex of the type $MABCDE$

The frame group F is S_5 and the site group A is isomorphic to subgroup H_{11} of S_5 . The ligand group $B = S_1 \times S_1 \times S_1 \times S_1 \times S_1$, which is isomorphic to subgroup H_1 of S_5 .

From rows 11 and 1 of Table 3.1,

$$\underline{m}(A) = (20, 0, 4, 2, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 2, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0)$$

and

$$\underline{m}(B) = (120, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0).$$

So

$$\underline{m}(A) \square \underline{m}(B) = (2400, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0)$$

Expressed as a linear combination of rows of Table 3.1,

$$\underline{m}(A) \square \underline{m}(B) = 20(120, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0)$$

,
so,

$$\underline{m}(A) \square \underline{m}(B) = 20\underline{m}(H_1).$$

Hence by Theorem 3.1, the complex has 20 stereoisomers with symmetry group conjugate to H_1 .

4. CONCLUSION

Results show that Iodotricarbonyl (triphenylphosphine) – cobalt (1) complex, $[CoI(CO)_3P(C_6H_5)_3]$ has 4 stereoisomers; three with symmetry group conjugate to H_1 and one with symmetry group conjugate to H_4 while of hydridocarbonylethylene (bis – triphenylphosphine) – rhodium (1) complex, $[RhHCO(P(C_6H_5)_3)_2C_2H_4]$ has 10 stereoisomers with symmetry group conjugate to H_1 . Finally, we showed that the trigonal bipyramidal complex of the type $MABCDE$ has 20 stereoisomers with symmetry group conjugate to H_1 .

REFERENCES

1. Burnside, W. (1911). Theory of groups of finite order, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge (Dover reprint 1955). ISBN-10: 0486600386, ISBN-13: 978-0486600383.
2. Ivanov, A. A., Klin, M. H., Tsaranov, S. V. and Shpektorov, S.V. (1983). On the problem of computing subdegrees of transitive permutation groups. *Soviet Mathematical Survey*; 38: 123 – 124. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1070/RM1983v038n06ABEH003460>
3. Kamuti, I. N. (1992). Combinatorial formulas, invariants and structures associated with primitive

permutation representations of $PSL(2, q)$ and $PGL(2, q)$, Ph. D. Thesis, Southampton University, U.K.

4. Kamuti, I. N. (2006). Subdegrees of primitive permutation representations of $PGL(2, q)$. *East African Journal of Physical Sciences*; 7(1/2): 25 – 41.
5. Kimani P., Rimberia J., Muthoka G., Lao H. (2014). Applications of marks to computation of ranks and subdegrees of the symmetric group acting on ordered pairs and ordered triples. *Journal of Mathematical Theory and Modeling*; 4:13 95-102. doi: <https://doi.org/10.7176/MTM>
6. Lloyd, E. K. (A). (1988). Redfield’s papers and their relevance to counting isomers and isomerizations, *Discrete Appl. Math.* 19: 289 – 304. doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0166-218X\(88\)90020-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0166-218X(88)90020-0)
7. Lloyd, E. K. (B). (1992). Marks of permutation groups and isomer enumeration. *Journal of Mathematical Chemistry*; 11 (1): 207 – 222. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01164205>
8. Redfield, J. H. (1984). Enumeration by frame group and range groups, *J. Graph Theory*; 8:205 – 233.
9. Rimberia, J. K and Kamuti, I. N. (2015). Subdegrees of Primitive permutation representations of the Symmetric Group S_5 , *International Journal of Scientific Research and Innovative Technology*; 2: 4, 26-33. ISSN: 2313-3759 (Online).
10. Sheehan, J. (1968). The number of graphs with a given automorphism group, *Canad. J. Math.* 20: 1068 – 1076. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1090/S0002-9939-1975-0349408-9>
11. White D. E. (1975). Counting patterns with a given automorphism group, *Proc. Of Amer. Soc.* 47:41 – 44. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1090/S0002-9939-75-99973-6>